

Morphological Development of Human Fetal Kidney: A Cross-Sectional Study in the North Eastern Region

Nirmalendu Das¹, Nani Gopal Das², Rajkumari Ajita³, Chongtham Rajendra Singh⁴

¹Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur, India

²Assistant Professor & HOD (IC), Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital

³Associate professor, Department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur, India

⁴Professor, Department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Nani Gopal Das

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Abstract:

Background: The morphological development of human fetal kidney have been subject of increased awareness for the assessment of fetal growth and development in a high risk pregnancy, prematurely delivered normal baby and also in prenatal diagnosis of renal diseases and possible intervention.

Objectives: The aim of the study was to determine the morphological development of the kidneys during the fetal period.

Methods: The present study was carried out in the department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur. The material for the study consisted of 60 spontaneously aborted and still born human fetal specimens free from any gross congenital anomalies with gestational age between 11th to 38th weeks were collected from Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, RIMS. The kidneys were taken out from fetal specimens and studied.

Results: Surface of the kidney is found to be lobulated from 13 weeks of gestation with gradual increase in lobulation and maximum number of lobulation was observed at 30 weeks thereafter a declination was noticed till the term pregnancy. The kidney of 11th and 38th weeks of gestation was observed to have smooth surface without any surface lobulation. Shape of the pyramid changes from nodular to triangular with advancing gestational age except at 11th of gestational age where the pyramid is not identifiable.

Conclusions: The present work made an initial attempt to analyze the morphological growth pattern of kidney in human fetuses, which may prove useful in defining the prematurely delivered normal baby, high risk pregnancies and fetal kidney diseases and age determination of fetuses during post mortem autopsy.

Keywords: Gestational age, Renal Development, Renal Pyramid, Surface lobulation.

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Introduction

Morphological development of kidney undergoes a continual and mutually dependent developmental changes through which obtains its structural and functional maturity [1]. It is very important to know the normal morphological development of kidney for prenatal diagnosis of renal anomalies, genetic counseling and treatment of prenatal renal disorders like Wilm's tumor, multicystic renal dysplasia and persistent fetal lobulation of kidney etc.

The accurate gestational age estimation is very important to an obstetrician for diagnosis of growth disorders, in assessment of wrong dates or forgotten dates and timing of delivery either by induction or caesarean section. It is particularly important in high-risk pregnancies (severe preeclampsia, chro-

nic hypertension, severe IUGR, central placenta previa, sensitized Rh-negative mother etc.) where in some cases early termination may become necessary as soon as fetus becomes mature [2].

Present study was undertaken to study the morphological differentiation of the kidney at different stages of development during fetal life. The aim of the study was to determine the morphological development of the human kidneys during the fetal period.

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out in the department of Anatomy, Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal, Manipur. The material for the study

consisted of 60 spontaneously aborted and still born human fetal specimens free from any gross congenital anomalies with gestational age between 11th to 38th weeks were collected from Obstetrics and Gynaecology department, RIMS after taking permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee and an informed consent was taken from the respective mother after fully explaining the purpose of the research work and categorized into 4 groups as Group-A(11-20 weeks), Group-B(21-27 weeks), Group- C(28-33 week), Group-D(34-38

weeks).The kidneys were taken out from fetal specimens for study.

Results

Morphological differentiation of the human fetal kidney at different gestational ages, from 11 weeks to 38 weeks has been studied. The fetuses were divided into four groups according to the gestational age. The detailed findings of the growth and development of the kidneys were as follows:

Figure 1: Fetal kidneys in different weeks of gestation

Group-A (11-20 weeks)

Figure 2: Smooth surface, 11 weeks kidney

Figure 3: Pyramid can't be identified, 11 weeks kidney

Figure 4: Lobulated surface, 14 weeks kidney

Figure 5: Nodular pyramids at 13 weeks kidney

- **Number of fetuses** = 19
- **Shape:** Bean shaped
- **Surface:** lobulated (Fig. 4) except the 11th week specimen (Fig. 2) which has smooth surface without any lobulation.
- **Shape of the pyramid:** Nodular (Fig. 5) except 11th week specimen (Fig. 3) where pyramid is not identifiable.

Group-B (21-27 weeks)

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Figure 6: Nodular Pyramid, 21 weeks kidney

Group-C (28-33 weeks)

Figure 7: Triangular Pyramid, 28 weeks kidney

- **Number of fetuses** = 17,
- **Number of fetuses**-13
- **Shape:** Bean shaped,
- **Shape-** Bean Shaped
- **Surface:** Lobulated
- **Surface-** Lobulated with maximum lobulation
- Observed on 30 weeks followed by gradual decline. (Fig-1)
- **Shape of the pyramid:** Nodular (Fig. 6) Shape of the Pyramid- Triangular (Fig. 7)

Group-D (34-38 weeks)

Figure 8: Smooth surface of 38 weeks kidney

Figure 9: Triangular pyramids of 38 weeks kidney

- **Number of fetuses** = 11
- **Shape:** Bean shaped
- **Surface:** lobulated except the 38th week specimen which is has a smooth surface without any lobulation (Fig. 8)
- **Shape of the pyramid:** Triangular (Fig. 9)

Discussion

The morphological study of fetal kidneys in this present work outlines the smooth surface having no lobulations at 11 weeks of gestational age, whereas lobulations were observed from 13 weeks in utero till 37 weeks which is in accordance with Hamilton and Mossman HW [3].

Sunitha V and Rao BN4 observed a smooth surface having no lobulations at 10 weeks which is a little earlier than the present study, also presence of lobulations at 14 weeks and fusion of the lobules was noted between 16-20 weeks of gestation and no lobules beyond 24 weeks of gestation, however in this study lobulations could be observed from 13 weeks to 37 weeks of gestation. Mishra S et al [5] observed that the fusion of lobules occurs in a fetus of 16 weeks of gestation though lobulation is still evident, similar as in this present study. Sharma S and Raina S [6] observed presence of lobulation in kidneys as early as 10 weeks and lobules start fus-

ing with each other at 15 weeks of gestation in contrary to our study where we have observed lobulations from 13 to 37 weeks and there was no gross surface lobulation at 11 weeks.

Abdulkadar S and Shameer VK [7] observed that surface lobulation maximum at 28 weeks, after which lobulation decreased in numbers little earlier than our study where we have observed maximum lobulations at 30 weeks and there was no gross surface lobulation at 38 weeks. Favorito LA et al [8] observed a linear correlation between the fetal renal surface lobulation and gestational age, similar to our study where lobulated surface of kidney observed from 13 weeks gestation with gradual increase in lobulation. Ryan D et al [9] conducted a study on autopsy samples of developing foetus highlight spatial and temporal variability in nephrogenesis in the developing human kidney, whereas the relative cellular composition of glomeruli does not appear to be influenced by gestational age.

Sune S [10] observed in her study conducted in Sawangi that the length, thickness and the circumference of the both the kidneys showed a steady rise over the period of gestational developmental age. The mean width of both the kidneys slows down in the growth as the gestation progresses.

Tank KC et al [11] found in their observation that all kidneys were lobulated, bean shaped and all the dimensions of kidney increased with increase in age and weight of foetus. Histologically, the smallest glomeruli were in the most superficial cortex and the largest in the juxtamedullary zone. Size of nephrogenic zone was decreasing while size of cortex and medulla increased with increase in fetal age. Ram KS et al [12] observed nephrogenic zone decreased as gestation advanced after 18th week of gestation. Cortico-medullary differentiation was seen in later gestational period. Joshi R et al [13] in their study observed that nephrogenic zone was found as broad band in early gestational weeks disappeared in late stages.

Halder A et al [14] and Kumar R et al [15] found that kidney is covered by a thick capsule made up of fibrous tissue beneath which cortico-medullary differentiation is well marked. Lobulation & medullary rays visible in cortex.

Conclusions

The knowledge on morphological growth pattern of kidney in human fetuses may prove useful in defining the prematurely delivered normal baby, high risk pregnancies under consideration of termination by the obstetrician and fetal kidney diseases including Wilms tumour, renal dysplasia, persistent lobular kidney for possible early intervention and age determination of age of the fetuses during post mortem autopsy.

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